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Microlearning to support authentic learning in continuing education and for engineering students

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1 INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly changing society, there is a growing demand for learning for innovation in organisations and engineering education. The increased global competition requires organisations and individuals to be qualified to quickly respond to changes in the market. Organisations and individuals must be capable of innovating - defining and solving novel, complex problems for which often no previous knowledge exists [1].

This paper is about microlearning as a format for learning in continuing engineering education to foster the use of authentic learning in dealing with real-world issues and

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innovation at the level of higher engineering education (HEE). The authors of this paper see learning as a contextual lifelong learning process which enables the construction of knowledge, finding new solutions to problems, creating connections between experiences, participation and learner control of the content and the process [2].

The microlearning method was developed to support predominantly informal learning activities in or close to the workplace, while avoiding the drawbacks of informality [3]. Microlearning helps to structure an on-demand approach to learning and performance in a flexible and self-directed way and facilitates organising short-cyclical learning practices at the workplace. From the experiences in the business environment it is assumed that microlearning has a lot of potential to stimulate the use of authentic learning in HEE [4]. Authentic learning practices in education have many benefits, as they bring real world problems, constraints and solution strategies in to the classroom. These learning practices though are not always easy to incorporate in existing teaching praxis, as they are time consuming, difficult to organise, expensive or too complicated. Microlearning supplies a format that help to facilitate authentic learning from a content and organizational point of view.

2 RESEARCH CONTEXT

2.1 The bigger picture

A daunting issue in Europe is skill shortages. Such gaps arise where the skills required are unavailable in the workforce, due to for example technological advance. If people are over- or under skilled, whatever their qualification level, their skills do not match the job [5]. One way to mitigate this mismatch is to forge stronger links between institutions and industry like structured partnerships such as 'knowledge alliances' to adapt curriculum to demands of society. Therefore, good engineering education relies on real life learning and the ability to communicate and collaborate, which demands students to be self-developers in a continuous improvement process [6]. Authentic settings can be helpful to augment the understanding of innovation and entrepreneurship in real life and microlearning can be a catalyser for the incorporation of authentic learning in the HEE context.

2.2 The focus of this paper

The focus is on exploring microlearning as a format to support authentic learning in HEE with the aim to acquire relevant knowledge, labour market skills and attitudes relevant for innovation in a workplace setting. To achieve this, we describe a series of microlearning experiences in a large energy company that were intended to support continuous innovation within the company and use this information to deduce lessons for HEE. In section 3 we describe the origins of microlearning and the basic structure of the method. In section 4 we report on the experiences within the company and in the final section there is a reflection on the lessons for HEE.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Learning for innovation

Technological innovation has made our society knowledge intensive and successful performance of individuals or groups heavily relies on the acquisition and utilization of relevant information and suitable communication to achieve task objectives. Many authors agree that innovation is rooted in people's tacit knowledge and arises through non-planned

bottom-up initiatives as a result of day-to-day experiences. Tacit knowledge is difficult to transfer without close personal contact, demonstration, involvement and to be communicated and shared within the organization, it has to be made explicit somehow [7]. Key element for learning for innovation is creating interaction that support social learning, participation and bridge the gap between employees with various responsibilities in the organization.

Learning within organisations is difficult, but vital not only for newcomers but also for experienced employees and for experts. Students often come to the workplace ill-prepared: their competences may not always match with the demands, demands change rapidly as a result of innovation, and the demands vary across Europe given the heterogeneity of industry, HEE and development policies. Furthermore, students often are not well-prepared to deal with the demands of innovation in organisations. It is of paramount importance that students are better prepared and have a firm understanding of practice when they leave their schools. The argument is that an authentic learning environment that mimics real life in the workplace is an effective way to improve the student's capability to cope with learning demands at the workplace. Microlearning is an authentic way of learning in the workplace and, as such, is a promising format for learning in today's HEE that aims to prepare students for an ever-evolving future.

3.2 Authentic learning and self-directed learning

Authentic learning gives learners opportunities to think and act like professionals in a learning or training context. Exposure to a real-life context with topics that are relevant and applicable in their prospective working environment prepares them with practical and useful knowledge and skills and has a beneficial effect on motivation [8]. Herrington and Oliver state that authentic learning environments enable students to feel involved in a project as part of a larger whole with tasks that could never be carried out individually and with a stimulus for (higher) thinking processes through communication and discussion [9]. The emergence of the internet and other new tools for communication, visualization, and simulation have lowered the threshold to develop and use authentic learning environments. In a physical sense it is easy to organize, but in a pedagogical sense it needs a clever design to deal with tasks and limitations imposed by the curriculum and institutional constraints [10].

Another important notion of authentic learning is the concept of self-direction. Self-Directed Learning (SDL) is not a clearly delineated, linear process, but a rather informal and self-directed way of meeting personal learning demands. It is a process of which the outcome will be evaluated by the learners themselves in the context of the workplace setting [11]. This ability for SDL is important for students but requires different behaviours in the setting of a workplace. To facilitate SDL, educational activities need to be designed in such a way that people, albeit individuals or groups, have space to discuss their own goals and work towards them.

3.3 Microlearning

The term microlearning, microteaching or microtraining, has been around in various forms and is currently viewed as a new way of responding to the growing need of learning on demand at the workplace and beyond [12]. Microlearning can be delineated as a pragmatic approach to lifelong learning due to its capability to support flexible learning that can be

easily integrated into everyday activities, supporting individual learning aims and needs [13]. Microlearning consists of a number of short, customized learning sessions for a group of employees with the focus on workplace-related learning demands with high practical relevance. The main goal of microlearning is to establish an effective way of active learning using short learning sessions with a minimum of interruptions of the regular workflow. Anyone at the workplace can initiate and organize microlearning on the basis of current needs and demands. The sessions are self-directed: the participants are not consumers of an activity but are expected to be highly involved in all parts of the process. This is essential to accomplish sustainable learning outcomes. Furthermore, to facilitate the active self-regulated learning activities, the organization needs to allow individual learning to take place as part of the daily workflow, rather than by hierarchical control and standardized set ups.

As presented in figure 1 a microlearning session typically comprises a time span of 15-20 minutes, which fits easily in the daily work process. It can activate and maintain learning processes for a longer period when they are bundled up in series, either face-to-face, online or in an e-learning situation (figure 2). Each session starts with an activating activity, followed by a demonstration or exercise. Next there is time for feedback or a short discussion on the exercise, and each session is concluded with directions for further development and a brief preview of the next sessions. Microlearning incorporates elements of the classic direct-instruction model but does not follow all the steps because of time constraints in the organisational context of the sessions.

Fig. 1. The structure of a microlearning session (based on [14]).

Figure 2 shows how a series of microlearning sessions can be organized. A series of multiple short learning situations, bundled up to one microlearning series, can foster an active process of knowledge gathering and sharing.

Fig. 2. A series of microlearning sessions (based on [14]).

4 MICROLEARNING: A CASE DESCRIPTION

The microlearning method has been developed and tested over a period of years in various organisations in an iterative improvement process. Previous to our current research there were three consecutive cycles of microlearning projects, following a step-wise approach in developing and testing the microlearning method to suit the context and focus of specific goals. This was done in close collaboration with over fifty partner organisations (universities and industries) in five European countries over the course of two Leonardo da Vinci Lifelong Learning projects. The microlearning method has been refined and applied in practice in the aftermath of these projects.

In this paper one of these microlearning experiences is presented to bring out the value for continuing and authentic learning, combining the issues of workplace learning, self-directed learning, and collective learning. This case study was executed in a large multinational energy company. The case-study research method as described by Yin [15] is applied here as a suitable method to study complex social and contemporary phenomenon in a real-life context and adheres as such to the organizational context which is a crucial condition for determining the success of the microlearning method. The main objective was to test microlearning for its usability in the operational business context and to develop insights in how to scale up and facilitate microlearning if the 'proof of concept' project was successful.

4.1 Set up of the evaluation

The purpose of the evaluation was to analyse the achievements in line with the goals of the 'proof of concept' phase. In the evaluation both the learning process of the participants as well as the organisation and execution of the microlearning method - were considered. The series of sessions carried out in the company were about lean production and maintenance.

Qualitative data were collected using a quick scan interview with the main stakeholders at the start and a concluding interview at the end of the experiments. A project diary was used to keep track of the experiences during the coaching activities of the researchers, their participation and observations. Quantitative data were collected using short questionnaires for the management, the initiator and the prime user. In addition, the initiators of the sessions prepared and described the design of the sessions on work sheets. In total six series of sessions took place. The employee's qualification of microlearning were summarized and used as input for the concluding interviews of the researchers with the employees.

4.2 Preparations

The prime users, the initiators and conductors of the sessions, were trained to use the microlearning method and coached in their first use of the method in practice. Each microlearning series of sessions was prepared with the initiator, being a change manager or co-worker, who organized the microlearning activities. Microlearning was introduced as a mechanism to support informal learning practices, adding flexibility and dynamism in a process where the employees were expected to be fully engaged throughout the process. A prerequisite therefore was to involve the primary stakeholders from the beginning on and familiarize them with the method in an operational way, having them acquiring the skill to convene a session. Tapping into motivational behaviour of employees was considered to be a prominent driver.

The prime users adapted the microlearning method and tools to the specific requirements of the maintenance department of a chemical plant. Different user groups were identified based on the kind of problems they wanted to work on using microlearning. In most cases the employees wanted to solve a specific inefficiency, like dust pollution, welling issues, and storage for machine parts. The selection of issues served as an example of how microlearning can be used for 'lean' purposes. The other employees, usually co-workers, were introduced to microlearning during an introductory session, mostly the first of a series of sessions on solving a shared problem.

4.3 Results

The employees experienced microlearning as a flexible method concerning the selection of issues to be addressed, the urgency or complexity of the issue and the organisation and planning. The microlearning method was considered a clear, easy-to-learn process structure with the capacity to take effective action. The series of sessions supported experiential learning, viewed as a process of making generalizations and conclusions about the learning experiences. The employees experienced a clear relation between the selected issue, their motivation and the learning process. In short, microlearning captured their interest, because of the direct link between the observed need, the process and the end-result.

The outcome of the questionnaires, the project diaries and interviews showed various relevant aspects for the use of microlearning as an alternative to existing learning practices on the work floor and in HEE.

Motivation: Microlearning motivated management and prime users and energized employees, who highly appreciated the lean solutions and the fact that their expert knowledge was addressed as a relevant input. Employees were reinforced and supported the knowledge sharing process.

Achievement of goals: The goals set for the microlearning sessions were achieved to a reasonable extent. For example: Employees used microlearning to solve an inefficiency related to dust pollution. The impact was easily measured by looking at the number of machine failures due to dust pollution over a period of time and compared to previous data.

Organizing microlearning at the workplace: The 'knowledge owners' communicated and gave feedback, the participants shared knowledge and took 'quick learning steps', which supported the workplace learning process considerably.

Relevance of the learning for their work: The learning was considered reasonable and relevant mainly because this was about workplace related issues resulting in concrete actions ("no monologues"). The structure allowed for issues to be repeated by others. The impact will be even greater when the users are more experienced with the teaching and learning method. "Colleagues should be able to feel comfortable using this method".

Time spend: Effective time spending, since meetings took place at the workplace where employees demonstrated and applied their knowledge timewise in line with the microlearning approach.

Learning climate: A positive effect on currently used methods was that the structure and conciseness of microlearning were incorporated to share knowledge in other settings (e.g. in toolbox meetings).

Next step: Microlearning is not yet a 'habit' or 'automatism'. Next step is integration of the learning method in the currently used methods for workplace learning (also as part of performance actions) to support a more process-oriented learning environment.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

This paper was about the question if and how microlearning can contribute to the construct of an authentic learning environment in HEE. The case study revealed that microlearning as a way to support informal and self-directed learning in an organisation, motivated both employees and management. Microlearning was applied to cover different demands by different users and showed to be purposeful to involve employees in an activating way, dealing with their learning needs in a timely manner.

The conclusion can be that the short-cyclic microlearning method can be beneficial for employees in organisations to support workplace learning, but also for students in HEE to support authentic learning. The important ingredients for successful microlearning are self-directedness of the participants, the ownership of the learning demand, the incorporation of existing knowledge and experiences. Microlearning is a format that is flexible in focus and can deal with a variety of topics. Once people are familiar with the format, they can use it to work on many different issues. There is a lot of potential for this format in problem-based learning sessions for students of various levels of their programmes. With students who do not have sufficient knowledge the initiator and or coach could be more directive in how to progress or the format could be applied to explore what knowledge is still missing within the team. For student teams, either in PBL or in other kinds of project work, who are more advanced in knowledge this method is fit to work on problems and innovations they need in their projects. They can use microlearning as a way to accelerate their work. They will not only improve their efficiency as a team, but will understand how to support continuous learning in a self-directed way.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Nonaka, I., & Takeuchi, H. (1995). *The knowledge-creating company: How Japanese companies create the dynamics of innovation*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- [2] Gabrielli, S., Kimani, S., and Catarci, T. (2016). The design of microlearning experiences: A research agenda. In: T. Hug, M. Lindner, & P. A. Bruck, (Eds.), *Microlearning: Emerging concepts, practices and technologies after E-learning: Proceedings of Microlearning Conference 2005: Learning & Working in New Media* (pp. 45-53). Innsbruck, Austria: Innsbruck University Press.
- [3] De Vries, P., and Brall, S. (2008). Microtraining as a Support Mechanism for Informal Learning. *eLearning Papers*, 11 (November).
- [4] De Vries, P., and Van den Bogaard, M. (2009). A Contemporary Educational Model for Lifelong Learning Practices. In: Lappalainen, P., & Markula, M. (Eds.), *European*

Continuing Engineering Education, conceptualizing the lessons learned (pp. 209-218). Finland, SEFI and TKK Dipoli

- [5] Cedefop (2015), *Skills, Qualifications and Jobs in the EU: the making of the perfect match*. Luxembourg: Publications of the European Union.
- [6] Moropoulou, A. and De Vries, P., On the Problems, Challenges and Prospects for the European Higher Engineering Education arising from the global economic Crisis, In: Come, F., e. a. (2013). *SEFI@40 Driving Engineering Education to Meet Future Challenges*. Brussels. Pp. 81-85.
- [7] Polanyi, M. (1967). *The Tacit Dimension*, New York: Anchor Books. (108 + xi pages).
- [8] Lombardi, M. (2007). Authentic learning for the 21st century: An overview. In D. G. Oblinger (Ed.), *Educause learning initiative*.
- [9] Herrington, J., and Oliver, R. (2000). An instructional design framework for authentic learning environments. In: *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 48(3), 23-48.
- [10] De Vries, P., Kortmann, R., & Van den Bogaard, M. E. D. (2012). An Authentic Learning Strategy for Engineering Students to acquire Integrated Management Competencies. In *Proceedings of 40th Annual SEFI conference, 23-26 Sept 2012, Thessaloniki, Greece*. Thessaloniki: SEFI.
- [11] Margaryan, A., Milligan, C., Littlejohn, A., Hendrix, D., and Graeb-Koenneker, S. (2009). Self-regulated learning and knowledge sharing in the workplace. *Proceedings of International Conference on Organisational Learning, Knowledge and Capabilities*, 1–15.
- [12] Anil Job., M. and Slade Ogalo, H. (2012). Micro Learning As Innovative Process of Knowledge Strategy. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 1(11), 92–96.
- [13] Buchem, I. and Hamelmann, H. (2010). Microlearning: a strategy for ongoing professional development Microcontent and Microlearning. *E-Learning Papers*, 21 (September 2010), 1–15.
- [14] Overschie, M.G.F. (2007). Final report Microteaching project: Sustainable Technological Development, *EU Leonardo da Vinci Lifelong Learning project*.
- [15] Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. London UK: Sage Publications.